

ELECTRICAL RESPONSES OF THIN-PLY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a preliminary experimental investigation into understanding the effects of ply thickness on electrical responses of nickel-coated carbon fibre reinforced composites. Nickel-coated carbon fibre reinforced composite laminate plates were fabricated using plies of different thickness, i.e. 0.02, 0.03, 0.08 and 0.1 mm, respectively. Electrical resistivity was measured along longitudinal, transverse and through-the-thickness directions for laminates with and without tensile loading. The influence of ply thickness on damage behaviour of thin- and normal-ply composites subjected to an impulse of large electrical current was also experimentally investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRP) are widely used in aerospace, automobile and energy sector because of its high specific stiffness and strength and other superior properties. However, epoxy-based CFRP usually possess very high electrical resistivity or low electrical conductivity due to the insulating nature of epoxy that encloses and separates carbon fibers.

The conductivity of CFRP in the thickness direction is typically in the range of 10^{-3} - 10^0 S/m, which is much smaller than that of carbon fiber itself. Surface modification of carbon fibers (CF), such as CF grafted by carbon nanotubes (CNT) and the surface metallization of CF, is one of the methods developed to improve CFRP's electrical conductivity. There are some works available on measuring and understanding the mechanisms of electrical conductivity of CFRP [1-3].

Fiber distribution in CFRP is an important factor affecting overall properties of CFRP, including mechanical and electrical properties. It has been shown that thin ply CFRP has some notable benefits in particular in enhancing some mechanical properties when compared to traditional normal ply CFRP [4-6]. There is little understanding about the effects of ply thickness on electrical resistivity or conductivity of CFRP made from normal and thin plies. This study aims to address this issue.

In this study, presented first is an in-house developed CF filament spreading process to prepare nickel-plated carbon fibers (Ni-CF) reinforced epoxy plies of different thicknesses, ranging from 0.02 mm to 0.1 mm. Unidirectional laminates were prepared using such plies with four different ply thickness, microstructures of such CFRP were studied and the electrical resistivity of the prepared multiple-ply CFRP and single-ply laminates was measured. It was found that an decrease in ply thickness tends to reduce the contents of resin rich pockets, electrical resistivity and the associated anisotropy.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Sample Preparation

The material used was 12K T700 nickel-plated carbon fiber (Ni-CF) tow as shown in Fig. 1(a). A Ni-CF with a nominal diameter of 7.5 μ m typically has an electrical resistivity of 1.0×10^{-4} Ω cm and a measured tensile strength of 4.5 GPa. As shown in Fig. 1(a), a 12K Ni-CF tow was spread into the desired width of 20, 30, 60 and 80 mm by using an in-house developed equipment based on the pneumatic concept of modulating air flow and its interaction with CF tow and filaments similar to that reported in [4]. As shown in Fig. 1(c), the spread fiber filaments are carefully controlled and guided directly into the coating rollers where the epoxy is infiltrated into the fiber uniformly under the

protection of release paper and PET film. In this study, 2592 epoxy resin from Toray was uniformly coated on a lower release paper. The spread Ni-CFs were then laid on the lower release paper and covered with an upper release paper. The thickness of one single ply from a 12K tow by spreading to 20, 30, 60 and 80 mm in width was estimated to be 0.1, 0.08, 0.03 and 0.02 mm, respectively. The resin weight fraction was set to be 40% with an error of $\pm 1\%$. After removing the release paper and PET film, prepreg tapes of 0.1, 0.08, 0.03 and 0.02 mm thick were prepared as shown in an illustrative example in Fig.1(c).

The prepreg tapes in different thickness and width were then used to prepare specimens for evaluating their electrical responses. Two types of specimens were prepared. The first one was single-ply composite plates, and the second was multiply ply laminates of 1 mm thick.

The single-ply was cured in a vacuum molding machine. The curing temperature was 120°C, the pressure was 0.5-1 MPa relevant to the ply thickness and the curing time was 120 minutes. The mold used is shown in Fig. 2. In order to improve the performance of gas removal during curing process, small holes with a diameter of 1 mm were drilled on the walls of the mold. Fig.2(b) illustrate a single ply test sample.

Figure 1: Manufacturing procedure of ultrathin Ni-CF reinforced epoxy tape. (a) tow spreading steps; (b) epoxy coating of spread Ni-CF tow on release paper; (c) fabricated prepreg tape

Figure 2: (a) the molds used in fabricating samples of different thickness; (b) the prepared sample

Four unidirectional laminates of the size 270x260x1mm³ were prepared by using the prepreg plies of different thickness and by using the same fabrication method of curing the single-ply specimen. Each of the fabricated laminates was cut into two types of multi-ply laminate specimens: (a) the first

type specimen of the size 15 mm × 15 mm was used to measure the electrical resistivity of the CFRP subjected to no loading; (b) the second type of the size 250 mm × 15 mm was used to measure the electrical response of CFRP under tensile loading.

All specimens were dried in vacuum oven at 80°C for one hour prior to measurement.

2.2 Testing Method and Procedures

For the multi-ply laminate specimens, their typical cross-sectional microstructures were firstly examined by using an optical microscope (Zeiss, Germany). By using these optical microscopic images, the distribution of resin-rich pockets, for example, larger than 40 μm² was studied and the associated ratio was determined by using a statistical method.

Electrical resistivity in through-the-thickness and in-plane longitudinal and transverse directions for each of the single-ply and multi-ply laminate specimens was measured with a Tektronix meter 4050 (USA) by using the four-probe method. As shown in Fig. 3, electrically conductive silver tape and copper foil were pasted on the opposite faces to measure the associated relevant resistivity. A pair of glass plates of 2 mm thick each was adhered to the opposites faces of the specimens to measure the electrical resistivity in the in-plane longitudinal and transverse directions as shown in Fig.3(a).

Figure 3: Schematics showing set-ups used for measuring the electrical resistivity along the in-plane directions (a) and in through-the-thickness direction (1: heating base plate; 2: metal foil; 3: glass mat; 4: sample; 5: electrical resistance meter).

The resistive response of the multi-ply laminate specimen subjected to tensile loading at a rate of 1 mm/minute was measured using a CRIMS universal testing machine integrated with Tektronix 4050 Meter and digital image correlation DIC. The test set-up is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Specimen dimension and test setup for measuring electrical resistivity under tensile loading.

In addition, matrix micro cracking and fiber breakage inside the laminate specimen at higher tensile loading was also recorded by using an acoustic emission system.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Cross-sectional Micro Structures

Fig. 5 depicts the typical optical microscopic images of the cross-sectional microstructures of each of the four multi-ply unidirectional specimens laminated with different ply thickness. It is evident that, as the ply thickness increases from 0.02 mm to 0.1 mm, individual plies become more and distinguishable with resin-rich layer between two adjacent plies becoming more obvious.

The associated ratio of the resin-rich pockets larger than $40 \mu\text{m}^2$ in a representative volume element (RVE) was calculated using a statistical method, and they are 3.6%, 2.5%, 1.9% and 1% for the specimens prepared using 0.1, 0.08, 0.03 and 0.02 mm thick plies respectively. This indicates that specimens prepared using thicker plies would have larger amount of resin-rich pockets.

Figure 5: The microstructure of the laminate cross-section with prepregs of different thickness.

3.2 Electrical Resistivity

The measured average electrical resistivity in the fiber (longitudinal), the transverse and through-thickness directions are $0.07 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$, $2.2 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ and $151.6 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ respectively for the $15\times 15\times 1$ mm specimens prepared using 0.1mm thick plies. These values decrease to 0.6 and $31.9 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ respectively for these specimens made from 0.02mm plies in the transverse and through-the-thickness directions, and almost without change in the fiber direction. In light of the measured results in Section 3.1, it can be speculated that specimens with larger amount of resin-rich pockets would have higher electrical resistivity in both in-plane and through-the-thickness directions. It can be concluded that reducing ply thickness can reduce the context of resin-rich pockets, which subsequently can reduce electrical resistivity of the CFRP.

The electrical resistivity in the longitudinal (fiber), transverse and through-thickness directions for the single-ply specimens was measured and determined. There were two sets of measurements conducted: one without removing surface epoxy and the other with surface epoxy being removed.

Table 1 lists the average results in the three directions with B and A referring to the results before and after removing surface epoxy layer. The results in Table 1 reveal that the resistivity in the longitudinal and transverse directions of the single-ply specimen appears to be almost not affected by the variation of ply thickness. The resistivity in the thickness direction for specimens with surface epoxy layer being removed decreases slightly with an increase in ply thickness, but it is almost independent to the thickness similar to resistivity in the two in-plane directions. However, the resistivity in the thickness direction increases significantly with the ply thickness for the specimen with the surface epoxy layer not being removed, which illustrates the influence of the resin-rich epoxy layers on the upper and lower surfaces of the ply.

Ply thickness (mm)	0.02	0.03	0.08	0.1
Longitudinal direction (B &A)	0.06	0.08	0.05	0.05
Transverse direction (B &A)	0.11	0.11	0.1	0.1
Thickness direction (B)	26	43	122	120
Thickness direction (A)	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2

Table 1. Average measured electrical resistivity ($10^{-1} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$) in longitudinal (fiber), transverse and thickness direction for single-ply samples

3.3 Influence of Tensile Loading

Fig. 6 depicts the variations of electrical resistivity in through-thickness direction versus the applied tensile load for the four multi-ply laminate specimens of 250 mm by 15 mm prepared using plies of four different thickness. and loaded in tension, and the corresponding electrical resistances in both directions were measured as shown in Fig. 4. It is noted that the electrical resistivity in the thickness direction increases with the applied tensile load, and the increase in resistivity for the specimens prepared with thick plies are larger than those with thin plies. These results indicate that the electrical resistivity in the thickness direction for specimens with thick plies appears to be more sensitive to the applied tensile load, in particular when the applied load is greater than 23 kN. It is believed that the content of large resin rich pockets could be a contributing factor as at higher load level, matrix micro cracking initiates and accumulates as the applied load reaches certain level of 23 kN or tensile stress level of 1.533 GPa for the specimens considered.

Figure 6: Effects of tensile load on electrical resistivity in through-thickness direction

Fig. 7 depicts the energy amplitude (in the range of -1 to 1 V) of events (hits) recorded by the acoustic emission system and the associated strain levels for the multi-ply laminate specimens

prepared with thin plies (0.02 mm) and normal plies (0.1mm). A comparison between the event energy amplitude variations in Fig. 7(a) and (b) reveals that: (a) when strain level is above 1%, both the frequency and energy amplitude of events (hits) for the 0.1 mm sample are larger than those for the 0.02 mm sample, indicating more frequent occurrence of more severe micro matrix cracking and fibre breakage in the 0.1 mm sample than in the 0.02 mm sample; (b) the recorded acoustic events tend to occur earlier in the 0.1 mm sample comparing to 0.02 mm sample (except for one isolated event at about 165). It is noted that the thin-ply appears to suppress the development of micro crack in the UDL and thus delay or reduce the fiber breakage, which is believed to be the main contributing factor for the observation that thin-ply composites tends to exhibit stable electrical performance under tensile loading.

(a) 0.02 mm thin-ply

(b) 0.1 mm thin-ply

(c) Strain-time curves

Figure 7: Results of the acoustic emission: counts of event for (a) 0.02 mm thin-ply sample and (b) 0.1 mm thick-ply sample; (c) strain-time curves for thin- and thick-ply samples

3.4 Damage due to Impact Current

In order to further evaluate the effects of ply thickness on the electrical behavior of the samples, we conducted a current impact test to the 250x15x1 mm samples under a constant tensile load of 6kN. The test setup used for this test is the same as those presented in Fig. 4 except for removing the acoustic emission system. An electrical current impulse as shown in Fig. 8(a) with a maximum amplitude of 3kA maintained for a duration of 20µs was applied to the UDL simultaneously at the two electrode locations as shown in Fig. 4. The electrical current was applied repeatedly and continuously for 50 times with no interval between two adjacent impulsive current impacts if the charging period at the end of each impulse cycle is included as in Fig. 8(a). There were in total four samples, i.e. two

0.02 mm samples and two 0.1 mm samples. Fig. 8(b) and (c) depict the images of the samples at different current impacts. These images indicate that the thick ply samples exhibit more severe visual damage on the surface than thin ply samples.

(a) Schematic of the applied electrical current impulse

(b) thin-ply sample

(c) thick-ply sample

Figure 8: Images of 0.02 and 0.1 mm samples subjected repeated electrical current impacts

Fig. 9 depict the test set-up for C-scanning the four tested samples and the C-scan images showing damage. The total damage area was measured first for each specimen, and then ratio of the total damage area to the total specimen area was calculated and they are 38.2% and 44.5% for the thin-ply (0.02 mm) and think-ply (0.1 mm) samples. This preliminary result reveals that the thin-ply samples suffer slightly lower damage than the thick-ply samples.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study presents preliminary experimental results the influences of ply thickness on electrical resistivity and response of CFRP. An in-house equipment was developed and verified for fabricating prepreg via tow spreading. Electrical resistivity in longitudinal, transverse and thickness directions for samples prepared using plies of different ply thicknesses were measured. The influence of tensile loading on electrical resistivity in thickness direction of samples with four different ply thicknesses

was also studied. A preliminary study on the influence of ply thickness on damage extent in multi-ply laminates when subjected to an impact large electrical current.

Figure 9: (a) C-scan setup for the four tested samples; (b) C-scan images of the four samples for damage measurement

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